

Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with 1-Hydroxymethyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic Acid and Heterocyclic Amines

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With 1-hydroxymethyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid (HmMPzH_2) as primary ligand, mixed-ligand complexes of the types, $\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{B} \cdot \text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{M} = \text{Co}/\text{Ni}$; $\text{B} = \text{H}_2\text{O}$, NH_3 , *py*, *pico*(α, β, γ); $\text{B} - \text{B} = o$ -phen/*dipy*; $n = 0, 2$] have been isolated and characterised in solid state. Magnetic and electronic spectral data classify all the mixed-ligand complexes as normal pseudo-octahedral ones. Ir data indicate that the primary ligand (HmMPzH_2) behaves as a monoprotic bidentate (N-O) one, through the carboxylic acid function with deprotonation and the pyrazolyl (tertiary) ring nitrogen, whereas the hydroxymethyl group present in 1-position of the pyrazole ring does not take part in complex formation under the experimental conditions.

It has long been well documented in several instances that the nucleophilicity of the nitrogen atoms and their steric accessibility may be varied through appropriate ring substitution, mainly in 1 or 3 (5) positions of the pyrazole ring, with significant change in the ligational behaviour of the resulting molecules. As a part of our programme^{1,2} of investigating the coordinating properties of substituted pyrazoles, the title ligand, viz. 1-hydroxymethyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid (Fig. 1) having in its structure the coordinating functions of tertiary ring nitrogen, the carboxylic oxygen and the hydroxymethyl oxygen (a potential tridentate ligand) has been synthesised in our laboratory with a view to study its complexation behaviour with cobalt(II) and nickel(II) salts.

Fig. 1

Experimental

Using the method of Huttel and Jochum³ adopted for the preparation of 1-hydroxymethyl-3,5-dimethylpyrazole, 1-hydroxymethyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid was prepared by the condensation of 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid* and formalin. The product, on recrystallisation from ethanol gave the pure sample as white flakes, m.p. 185-6° (Found: C, 48.19; H, 5.08; N, 17.85. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ calcd. C, 48.11; H, 5.20, N, 18.01%).

$\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, [$\text{M} = \text{Co}/\text{Ni}$]: To an ethanolic solution (30 ml) of metal(II) chloride

hexahydrate (0.01 mol) was added a solution of the ligand (0.02 mol, 3.2 g) in ethanol (30 ml). The resulting solution ($\text{pH} \sim 5$) was concentrated by heating at water-bath temperature and then left at room temperature when microcrystalline compound separated out. The product was filtered off, washed with cold water and alcohol, and finally dried in a desiccator over fused calcium chloride, (70-75%).

$\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, [$\text{M} = \text{Co}/\text{Ni}$; $\text{B} = \text{py}$, NH_3 , *pico*(α, β, γ); $n = 0, 2$]: To an ethanolic suspension of $\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002 mol in 30 ml) was added dropwise the respective base, when a clear solution was obtained ($\text{pH} \sim 6-7$). The resulting solution was concentrated to half of its original volume and then allowed to cool to room temperature, when the respective base adduct with varying shades separated out. In each case, the compound was collected and dried as before (50-70%).

$\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot \text{B} \cdot \text{B} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{M} = \text{Co}/\text{Ni}$; $\text{B} - \text{B} = \text{bipy}/o\text{-phen}$; $n = 0, 2$]: An ethanolic suspension of $\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH}_2)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002 mol, ~40 ml) was treated with a solution of 2,2'-dipyridyl (or *o*-phenanthroline) (0.002 mol) dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol followed by the dropwise addition of a dilute solution of ammonia to adjust the pH of the resulting solution around 7. The solution on concentration at water-bath temperature and on cooling to room temperature gave the desired compounds. These were collected as before.

Cobalt content of the complexes were estimated gravimetrically as anhydrous cobalt(II) sulphate. Nickel was estimated as nickel dimethylglyoximate. Estimations of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were carried out in the Microanalytical Laboratory of the Department. Molar conductance, magnetic susceptibilities, electronic (d.r.s. and solution) and

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Δ_m in DMF $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} at 302K B.M.
		M	N		
Co(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light pink	14.43 (14.56)	13.51 (13.92)	—	4.48
Co(L) ₂ .2py	Pink	11.11 (11.19)	15.85 (15.93)	15.21	4.40
Co(L) ₂ .2 α -pico.2H ₂ O	Light pink	10.02 (9.97)	14.04 (14.27)	18.32	4.70
Co(L) ₂ .2 β -pico.2H ₂ O	Rosy pink	9.78 (9.97)	13.99 (14.20)	22.81	4.65
Co(L) ₂ .2 γ -pico	Pink	10.56 (10.62)	15.01 (15.12)	20.52	4.98
Co(L) ₂ .dipy.2H ₂ O	Yellow	10.42 (10.51)	15.03 (14.96)	19.82	5.00
Co(L) ₂ .o-phen.H ₂ O	Yellow	9.82 (9.77)	13.78 (13.92)	21.57	5.20
Ni(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Light blue	14.21 (14.35)	13.62 (13.84)	*	2.98
Ni(L) ₂ .2NH ₃ .2H ₂ O	Greenish blue	13.19 (13.24)	18.97 (19.17)	**	3.34
Ni(L) ₂ .2py	Light blue	11.10 (11.02)	15.72 (15.96)	18.34	3.01
Ni(L) ₂ .2 α -pico.2H ₂ O	Light green	9.79 (9.82)	14.01 (14.23)	16.32	3.31
Ni(L) ₂ .2 β -pico.2H ₂ O	Light blue	9.95 (9.82)	14.12 (14.23)	15.31	3.30
Ni(L) ₂ .2 γ -pico	Light blue	10.49 (10.53)	15.03 (15.15)	20.61	3.32
Ni(L) ₂ .dipy	Light blue	11.00 (11.06)	15.82 (16.02)	22.32	3.22
Ni(L) ₂ .o-phen	Bluish pink	10.10 (10.24)	14.63 (14.83)	20.13	3.21

* L = HmMPzH.

** Conductance could not be measured due to insolubility of the complexes.

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Complex*	State	λ_{max} kK	Dq cm^{-1}	B cm^{-1}	β
Co(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Reflectance	9.0, 18.0(sh), 20.0	1015	810	0.83
Co(L) ₂ .2py	Reflectance DMF	9.5, 18.5(sh), 20.0 19.2(27.21), 20.8(23.8)	1068	792	0.81
Co(L) ₂ .2 α -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance DMF	9.5, 17.9(sh), 21.5 18.85(21.5)	1075	883	0.91
Co(L) ₂ .2 β -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance DMF	9.4, 15.8(sh), 21.0 19.86(26.21)	1072	861	0.88
Co(L) ₂ .2 γ -pico	Reflectance DMF	9.6, 18.85(sh), 20.4 19.2(26.43)	1060	787	0.81
Co(L) ₂ .dipy.2H ₂ O	Reflectance DMF	10.4, 18.7(sh), 20.8 18.2(25.34)	1150	767	0.74
Co(L) ₂ .o-phen.2H ₂ O	Reflectance DMF	10.4, 18.8(sh), 21.7 19.2(21.5)	1157	831	0.85
Ni(L) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Reflectance	10.0, 16.0, 23.0	1000	800	0.74
Ni(L) ₂ .2NH ₃ .2H ₂ O	Reflectance	10.0, 13.4(sh), 16.6, 25.0	1660	860	0.79
Ni(L) ₂ .2py	Reflectance DMF	10.4, 17.0 11.1(3.21), 16.1(18.44), 26.3(51.21)	1040	838	0.78
Ni(L) ₂ .2 α -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	9.5, 15.6, 25.0 16.4(13.1), 25.6(35.12)	950	900	0.83
Ni(L) ₂ .2 β -pico.2H ₂ O	Reflectance Methanol	10.9, 17.2, 20.8 10.2(5.2), 10.85(14.15), 16.3(13.61), 25.64(37.12)	1090	827	0.77
Ni(L) ₂ .2 γ -pico	Reflectance DMF	10.2, 12.9(sh), 17.2 10.8(14.15), 12.6(sh)(10.25), 16.4(18.09), 25.65(37.21)	1020	909	0.84
Ni(L) ₂ .dipy	Reflectance DMF	10.6, 13.3(sh), 17.8 12.96(4.17), 16.4(11.72), 25.65(37.31)	1060	990	0.91
Ni(L) ₂ .o-phen	Reflectance DMF	10.6, 12.9 ^a , 17.8 10.4(16.1), 15.8(15.66), 26.30(40.60)	1060	990	0.91

* L = HmMPzH.

** Sh = shoulder.

ir spectra of the complexes were recorded as described earlier⁵.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the mixed ligand complexes along with their colours, effective magnetic moments and molar conductance values are given in Table 1. The complexes are usually insoluble in common organic solvents but are soluble in donor solvents, like DMF. The molar conductance values of the complexes except the aquo species $M(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ lie in the range $15.21\text{--}22.81 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$, which point out that the species are non-electrolytes in the said solvent.

Cobalt(II) complexes: The magnetic moment values of the cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.40–5.20 B.M. (Table 1). The values, in some cases, are somewhat lower than those usually assigned for high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) species (4.8–5.2 B.M.). The data suggest that the complexes are octahedral ones with a symmetry lower than O_h . Critical examination of the magnetic moment values of the complexes $\text{Co}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reveals that there occurs a small but perceptible change in the magnetic moment values of the complexes, the μ_B value increases with increasing basicity of the co-ligand (B)⁶.

Reflectance spectral data of the present mixed-ligand complexes of cobalt(II) (Table 2) indicate an overall octahedral stereochemistry of the complexes. Two principal bands appearing in the region 9000–10400 and 20000–21700 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^4T_{2g}(\text{F}) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively in O_h symmetry. The relevant ligand field parameters, calculated through known relationships⁷, namely Dq (1015–1157 cm^{-1}), B (767–883 cm^{-1}) and β (0.74–0.91) point to an average octahedral environment in the complexes⁸. The B values which are significantly less than the free ion (970 cm^{-1}) values indicate considerable overlap and delocalisation of the d-orbitals of the metal. The additional spectral band around 17200–19000 cm^{-1} is not due to ν_2 transition but are likely to be arising from spin-forbidden transition, ${}^4T_{2g}(\text{G}) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{F})$ ⁹. In the DMF solution of the complexes, the spectral data are characterised by one main band around 18200–19200 cm^{-1} assigned to spin-allowed transition ${}^4T_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow {}^4T_{1g}(\text{F})$ (ν_2) in O_h symmetry. Nevertheless, the molar extinction coefficient ($\epsilon < 35$) of the spectral bands give an additional support to the octahedral nature of the complexes in solution.

Nickel(II) complexes: The observed room temperature magnetic moment values of the present nickel(II) complexes fall within the range 2.98–3.34 B.M. (Table 2) expected for the six-coordinated spin-free nickel(II) species, the somewhat higher value than the spin-only value (2.83 B.M.) of two

unpaired electron system, probably owing to a perturbation in symmetry and spin-orbital coupling.

The electronic spectra show two principal bands around 9500–10900 and 16000–17800 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to spin-allowed d–d transitions, ${}^3T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_1) and ${}^3T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ (ν_2) in O_h symmetry. The ν_2 band, corresponding to the transition ${}^3T_{1g}(\text{P}) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ expected for an octahedral nickel(II) complex could not be observed in the visible region (spectra recorded upto 26000 cm^{-1}) of the d.r.s. spectra of the complexes. The position of ν_2 band has, however, been computed and has been found to lie in all cases in the uv region, where it might be obscured by intense $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the ligand or intense charge transfer absorption arising from metal to ligand charge-transfer. The shoulder (or weak band) appearing near 13000 [viz. $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (134.0), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\gamma\text{-pico}$ (12900), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot \text{bipy}$ (13300), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot o\text{-phen}$ (13000 cm^{-1})] and 20800–25000 cm^{-1} [viz. $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (23000), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{NH}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (25000), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\alpha\text{-pico} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (25000), $\text{Ni}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\beta\text{-pico} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (20800 cm^{-1})] may be attributed to spin-forbidden transitions^{10,11}, $E_g(\text{D}) \leftarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g}(\text{D}) \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$, respectively. Dq values (taken directly from ν_1) fall in the range 950–1060 cm^{-1} and ν_2/ν_1 lie between 1.57–1.67; the data are consistent with pseudo-octahedral Ni^{II} species. The electronic spectral data in solution is consistent with an overall octahedral geometry showing two bands around 15800–16500 and 25600–26300 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ν_2 and ν_3 transitions, respectively in an octahedral environment.

Ir spectra: The characteristic band frequencies of the primary ligand (HmMPzH_2) along with major changes in its metal complexes give information regarding the bonding sites of the ligand molecules. The ir spectra of the metal complexes are, in general, complicated due to the presence of co-ligands. However, a careful scrutiny makes possible the following useful observations.

(i) The asymmetric OCO^- stretching frequencies of the free ligand appearing at 1710 cm^{-1} is shifted to a lower frequency region, viz. around 1630–1585 cm^{-1} in the metal complexes, while the symmetric stretching vibration appearing at 1425 cm^{-1} in the free ligand remains stationary or shows a little shift both ways in metal complexes. The data indicate the participation of the carboxylic group through deprotonation¹².

(ii) The bands at 1550 and 650 cm^{-1} in the free ligand are due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ and in-plane deformation of the pyrazole ring. A positive shift of $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ (by 20–30 cm^{-1}) and the in-plane deformation (by 15–20 cm^{-1}) of the pyrazole ring in the spectra of the metal complexes as compared to the uncomplexed ligand suggests the tertiary ring nitrogen atom as a potential bonding site¹³. The pyrazolyl-ring nitrogen atom is also established to be the bonding site from X-ray crystallographic studies of a number of pyrazole-metal complexes¹⁴.

(iii) The bands appearing at 1050 and 800 cm^{-1} in the free ligand due to $\nu_{\text{C-OH}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$ out of plane deformation of the CH_2OH group^{15,16} remain more or less stationary in the metal complexes. This suggests that the hydroxy methyl group in 1-position does not take part in the complex formation, probably due to the presence of a potential point of attachment (*viz.* the carboxylic group) in the 3(5)-position.

(iv) The presence of water (coordinated or lattice) molecules in the complexes has been pointed out by the appearance of one or more broad strong band(s) in the 3μ region, which may be attributed to the OH stretching mode of water molecule¹⁶, though this assignment is complicated due to the presence of CH_2OH group in 1-position of the ligand. In addition, the appearance of a medium strong band around 850-1000 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of $\text{M}(\text{HmMPzH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ indicate the presence of coordinated water molecule in these complexes¹⁷.

(v) The bands in the range 1425-1580 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the complexes containing pyridine and its methyl derivatives (picolines) as co-ligands and the bands at 1440-1480 and 720-860 cm^{-1} in the *o*-phenanthroline and dipyridyl adduct suggest their presence with usual coordination in the respective compounds^{18,19}.

(vi) New bands which are absent in the far-ir spectrum of the ligand, appear in the metal complexes at 370 and 250 cm^{-1} which may be assigned^{20,21} as $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N(py)}}$, respectively, thus adding valuable support to our proposition.

It appears, therefore, from the above discussion that the ligand 1-hydroxymethyl-5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid (HmMPzH_2) exhibits a mono-protic bidentate function through the tertiary (ring) nitrogen atom of the pyrazole ring and the carboxylic acid group through deprotonation, and the hydroxymethyl group unlike our previous observation² does not participate in bonding to a metal ion under the experimental conditions.

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